

AID IN REDISTRIBUTION OF SURFIET FOOD USING A WEBSITE

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ABSTRACT

The development of a website with solid value in developing countries, Its operation focuses on giving back to society, this is composed of five parts. The first part involves identifying the primary obstacles to overcome, such as limited food supply, insufficient funds, inadequate resources, and institutional deficiencies. The second part defines values the platform brings to the people who are in need. The third part proposes a way to connect the places that in need to the places which offers. The next part speaks about giving an option for the farmers to involve in a self-sufficient order of business dealing with the platform. This component also entails identifying the most suitable partnerships to upgrade the value of the platform. The last part describes about the farmers contributions transforming into a profitable point by processing them into value entailed raw materials and also about the pros and cons of the platform. This platform is based on prominent theoretical concepts related to inter-company relationships and developing country value chains.

Keywords: inadequate resources, farmer focused, hypertension, food supply.

INTRODUCTION

In India, the issue of food losses and waste is important in the efforts to combat hunger, raise income and improve food security. Food losses at the end of the food supply chain are considered food waste and are related to the behavior of retailers and consumers. A study conducted by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) found that food losses in different farm operations and the supply chain for cereals, pulses, oilseeds, fruits, and vegetables was 3.9% to 18% with a total monetary loss estimated at Rs. 44,000 crores

(USD 7,330 million). This high amount of loss highlights the need to minimize food losses and waste in India.

It is important to keep food losses and waste to a minimum in all countries, regardless of their level of economic development and maturity of systems.

Addressing food losses and waste is crucial in ensuring food security, sustainability, and improving the economy in India. Food insecurity is the inability to obtain enough food to lead an active and healthy life. Food and agricultural organization (FAO) stated that one third of all produced foods for human consumption is wasted every year [1]. Most recent survey indicates that 842 million people are chronically hungry in the world, 94 percent of it are from developing countries like India, China and other Asian countries [2]. Economic theories set indicators which reveals the impact of food waste in particular geographic conditions which unveils the underlying cause as lack of awareness of statistical data's among the generation [3]. Climatic variations seems to have an role in geography wise food insecurity [4]. Food shortages is linked to several developmental issues in children. Survey was taken among children corresponding to their performance in academics related to food shortages, it reported that affected social skills of the children performed amid food shortage, also their academic performance chart came down over time [5]. Food insecurity outcomes has its own grip over development in children. Food insecurity is tied with chronic disease including hypertension, hyperlipidemia, and diabetes. These chronic disease risk probability tends to increase over time in development phase in children going through food insecurity [6]. Developing a website would help in combating these problems in under developed countries, developing countries and even in the developed countries.

FOOD LOSES

Food loss is defined as “decrease in quantity or quality of food” and “agricultural or animal products intended for human consumption that are not ultimately consumed by humans.” However, according to FAO estimates, the quantity of food loss and waste globally is about 30 percent of cereals, 40–50 percent of root crops, fruits and vegetables, 20 percent of oilseeds, meat and dairy products, and 35 percent of fish (FAO, 2011). Total food losses globally have been estimated at 1.3 billion tons per annum (FAO, 2011). Food loss and waste mainly depend upon the specific conditions and local situation of the country. Food loss takes place at production, post-harvest and processing stages in the food supply chain. Food loss occurring at the end of food supply chain is rather called “food waste”, as it basically relates to the behavior of retailers and consumers. Food losses and their prevention have an impact on the use of scarce resources (water, land and energy), the environment, food security for poor people, food quality and safety, and the economy. Regardless of a country's level of economic development and system maturity, food loss and waste should be minimized. In India according to Longitudinal ageing study of India(LASI), with a sample of 30,000 older people whom are 60 years and above seems to have word recall problems relating to food insecurity. < 14% only are likely to avoid these problems which again depends on the food security [7]. Food insecurity among women are on high rise in India. Studies indicate that the presence of continual shocks and stresses have significant negative implications on food security [8]. Food insecurity tends to differ from urban and rural areas, a study found out that 7.7% of older adults reduce their meals size due to unavailability and for urban side 3.2% of them did not eat enough food of their choice.

It was also found that older adults who did not have enough food had significantly higher odds of suffering from cognitive impairment in reference to the control population of adults [9].

ACUTE FOOD LOSS

Rising population indirectly means acute food loss in long term, as world population is expected to reach 9-11 billion by 2050, concerns are rising about acute food loss among people [6]. Acute food loss refers to the sudden, unexpected, and significant reduction in the amount of food available for consumption due to natural disasters, conflict, economic shocks, or other factors. The effect of acute food loss can be severe, both in the short and long term, for individuals, households, communities, and entire countries. Short-term effects of acute food loss include malnutrition, hunger, and food insecurity. People who do not have access to enough food may experience physical and cognitive impairments, including stunted growth, weakened immune systems, and reduced ability to learn and work. Acute food loss can also lead to social and psychological consequences, such as anxiety, depression, and social unrest. In the long term, acute food loss can have severe economic consequences, particularly for small-scale farmers and vulnerable populations. It can also lead to environmental degradation, as farmers may be forced to cultivate marginal land or use unsustainable farming practices to increase production. Moreover, acute food loss can also have wider impacts on the global food system, particularly when it affects staple crops or major producing countries. For example, a major drought or flood in a key producing region can lead to global food price increases, affecting food security in other parts of the world. Food prices are now on the rise in markets across the globe which again has it's ties changing climatic conditions. Acute food shortages corresponds to increasing price in the market's . famine also plays a major role in this. This was stated in an article concentrating Kenya in the 1940's [10].

REASONS BEHIND FOOD LOSS

FL may occur during several phases of the value chain, including production, harvest, and post-harvest storage, transport, handling, and processing [11]. Food loss in India is influenced by a number of factors, including the country's supply chain and conditions. Some reasons for food loss in India include an inefficient and fragmented supply chain, a reliance on middlemen in handling raw produce, limited access to on-farm equipment and machinery, and inadequate cold storage capacity for perishable goods.

Additionally, the cold chain infrastructure in India is only available for certain products, such as milk, meat, and pharmaceuticals, and not for other commodities. Only 11% of the country's cold storage capacity is dedicated to storing produce, with 75.4% of available cold stores being used for potatoes. Additionally, there is limited access to refrigerated transportation from harvest to sale, with only 23.1% of cold stores being designated as multi-commodity stores. In the recent decade, India is one of the few nations to have done two rounds of thorough nationwide surveys on food loss. Since 1968, when the Panse Committee revealed 9.33 percent losses in selected food grains, the Union Government has led the evaluation of post-harvest losses. These included threshing losses (1.68 percent), transportation losses (0.15 percent), processing losses (0.92 percent), rodents (2.50 percent), birds (0.85 percent), insects (2.55 percent), and moisture (0.68 percent) [12].

FOOD WASTES

In India, there is a lot of worry about the issue of food waste. Wedding receptions, hotels, eateries, university and college canteens, household settings, and so on are a few of the biggest sources of food waste. The University of Agricultural Sciences (UAS), Bangalore, undertook a thorough investigation on food waste in 2011 since marriages in India result in a significant quantity of food waste [13]. 80 weddings were reportedly held at the 531 marriage rooms on average each year, with the average wedding taking place over two days. The event, where two meals are offered every function, was attended on average by 1000 individuals.

According to estimates, each plate included an average of 641 gram of food, of which 112 grams—or 18 percent in terms of physical quantity—were wasted. Typically, between 10 and 20 dishes are served throughout the event. Marriage receptions typically draw over 1000 guests, and each year, 943 tons of high-quality, calorie-dense food are wasted—enough to feed almost 26 million people a typical Indian dinner. According to the poll, a normal meal given is often fairly high in calories. A youngster might consume 1239 calories from food at each meal, which is enough to satisfy their needs for the full day. About 20 percent of this, or 246 calories, were squandered [14]. The two styles used at the wedding venues are buffet and served. Additionally, it was revealed that the buffet approach wastes more food (22% of what is offered) (20 percent). In the serving system, there is a 20% waste of rice and cereal. In high-budget weddings, there is a 35 percent loss of rice and other grains. In Bangalore City's 531 marriage halls alone, food waste is projected to cost Rs 3390 million (USD56.5 million).

CURRENT STRATEGIES IN COMBATING FOOD LOSS

Food waste can be mitigated to a great extent by creating awareness through mass media and other channels and campaigning in schools in order to create awareness among school children. We can also try to reduce food waste in our kitchen and in our plates. A mechanism may be developed under a public-private partnership mode to supply unused food to needy people. An NGO, the “Annakshetra Foundation”, during 2010 in Jaipur, developed a network of 500 hotels and marriage halls. The NGO collects the unused food, stores, checks for quality and finally distributes to the poor, slums or orphanages. This model has been replicated in Delhi, Mumbai and Vadodara. Fresh produce, including fruits and vegetables, but also animal products, can degrade quickly in hot climates, particularly in underdeveloped nations where there is a shortage of water and proper storage and transportation facilities. Several new technologies, such as solar dryers or a rice storage bag that blocks the flow of both oxygen and water vapour, have been developed to increase the life of products during storage, limiting post-harvest losses of this cereal by up to 15% as well as nutritional quality loss [15]. Another way is to apply modern technologies one such technology is, The International Rice Research Institute's (IRRI) “Super bag” is a storage bag that may be used to safely store grains and other crops (such as coffee) for extended periods of time. The bag can roughly double seed germination time, manage insects without the use of pesticides, and increase rice overhead recovery of stored grain by around 10% [16]. In developing countries, food losses are also attributable to the processing stage due to a lack of adequate processing facilities. Improved awareness of proper processing techniques, offering different sizes of packaging to meet different consumer needs and innovative packaging solutions, improving use-by date marking, and using food that cannot be intended for human consumption for feed or non-food uses can all be

used to prevent and reduce food losses in this sector [17].

AN ALL-OUT DEDICATING WEBSITE

The website prioritizes objective in connecting the people who are in need and the people who have an extra little of something. This way an impact is created on the society. This websites stands as an intermediate between the orphanages, old age homes, and charities andthe parties , marriages and donations.

Fig 1-Work flow of the website

This intermediary establishes a link that sustains both donator and receiver. The parties of both sides benefit from a good will. This way the need in society gets fulfilled with good deeds and inspires many souls to get involved in platform's motive and its entailed value. Operations start from the needy party raising a request in platform listing out the head counts and timings. The giving party raises a list of available food supplies and timings, website connects both parties by approving raised requests. This operation can be done regionally, locally and also sometimes can be done beyond borders with same principles.

FARMER FOCUSED STRATEGY

Currently technological global agri-food economies dominated by vertically integrated large enterprises are failing to meet the challenge of feeding a growing global population within the limits of the "Planetary Boundaries" and are marked by a "triple fracture" between agri-food economies and their three constitutive elements: nature, consumers, and producers [18]. As farmers are focused for potential benefits to both the platform and the suppliers (farmers). This website includes farmer focused profitable strategies which could ultimately generate a reasonable profit to sustain the business operation in a long range with solely relying on farmers which will improve their living. Strategy involves collection of agricultural feed wastes which includes premature vegetables and fruits from framers with providing equal incentives for their contributions and landing them in a local hub which is owned by the platform. Also, the waste foods from hotels are collected with equal incentives and route it to the local platform owned hub. Nothing goes into waste, even if all the need requests have been answered in the website. The collection hub acts swiftly as raw material processing plant concentrating the food wastes into raw materials following all governmental regulations. The term "community" serves as a vital link between small farms, agro-food SMEs, and the globalised urban market. A community is a system in which farming, value addition (e.g., processing and marketing),

distribution, and consumption are combined to improve a given region's environmental, economic, social, and nutritional form. The community method focuses on enhancing current or building new partnerships among all food system players, both internal (value chain) and external (social enterprise) [19].

FOOD WASTES TO ANIMAL FEEDS

Using food waste as animal feed provides a solution that solves waste management and food security issues while minimizing the need to generate traditional feed, which is both a resource and an environmental burden [20]. Food wastes are transformed into animal feed raw materials by biological means that don't interfere with the health of animals consuming it when it is mixed with regulatory feed components. This raw material formed from food wastes act like supplements that can promote the food product in the long run. Animal feed companies like "Santhi Feeds PVT LTD" can be targeted in marketing this raw material for their standard mixture convincing them to buy the product by offering in comparatively lower price than the usual raw materials also stating the products importance. This way the value of the website can be increased attracting more buyers. Marketing the products manufacturing process rather than focusing on the general advantages of it can increase the values of the feeds that are fed to animals, this will ultimately increase the value of the particular animal meat. This creates a demand to the animal feed companies from the meat suppliers, whom are demanded by the customers. Bioactive chemicals are molecules found in minute concentrations in meals that have the potential to deliver health benefits. Long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids, vitamins, carotenoids, peptides, and polyphenols are examples of bioactive substances [21]. Poultry is a significant component of livestock. Chickens are in great demand since they are tough creatures that develop quickly in most parts of the world. Chicken meat and eggs are important protein sources for many people across the world, as seen by the 25.2 MMT of chicken produced in the United States alone in 2017 and the estimated 83.9 MMT of grill output globally in 2018 [22]. A few nutrients that must be balanced in grill and layer diets include energy, crude protein, and crude fiber. As a result, when assessing for poultry feed animal wastes can be converted into these as they are rich in the chicken diets and are bio alternative for chemical feed raw materials. This demand ultimately turns to the website, which would increase the value of the product and reach could be great from such attractions. Following this strategy profitable income can be generated that could be put in good use for websites development into a firm that supports farmers, creates employment opportunities and benefits the society.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE WEB APP

Soul foods is an interconnecting website that aims in bringing the less and loss words ~~to~~ so that, the food that goes into waste is directed to people in need. This is a multidomain platform which both parties can register the requirements and extras. The website will automatically connect these two parties regionally or ping to the parties that are available to work with in a nearby distance.

The extra food will be collected from the providing party if it seemed to be decomposable or easily perishable then it would be directed to a processing hub that processes the food.

This hub will process the food wastes into animal feed stock and in for subsidized selling that would generate an income for the operation. These hubs will operate on wireless systems of autonomous temperature and

humidity sensors. These sensors would help in assessing the best possible conditions for the vegetables to prevent further deuteriation [23]. Processes foods in the storages are handles properly with active enzyme containing qualities which ensures the potential in the product for later use and ensures minimal wastes [24]. Fruits and vegetable is growing sector in India but the Supply chain is weak , this link is unreliable for the constant supply of waste foods and vegetables from farmers affecting the firm's operation and principle. Despite several steps taken by the Government of India to improve this cold chain, chain links still faces problems in their business operations [25]. The hubs will ensure the supply chain of horticultural products in India run flawless leading to a great outcome in terms of profits and continuous supplies in food wastes and horticultural wastes processing businesses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DATA COLLECTION

The users themselves provide all the necessary data for collection. Users can submit their needs and surplus using an easy-to-use interface that is compatible with all browsers. The gathered data is stored in a SQL database. Our admin confirms this information further by contacting the user or asking them to send documentation, such as photos and identity documents, to prove their identity. A typical user creates an account with us using a Google or Facebook account, followed by this he gives in additional information such as area of residence, identification proof, name, date of birth etc. Then he either chooses to be a "patron" or a "beneficiary". A patron is the one who donates his surplus, food or any other consumables. The patron goes into his/her app and fills in information about the food such as the type, quantity, date of manufacture/produce, estimated date of consumption. On the other hand, the beneficiary will give us details about their organization. The common data fields filled out by a beneficiary include the institution type (such as orphanages, senior living facilities, or disaster shelters, etc.), the number individuals present, its location, typical demography, average age group, and expected time of need. Every piece of data that is gathered is checked by an admin or a machine using evidence like pictures, videos, or phone calls. A notification is given to the user and the information is not shown on the website if it has not been verified. This process ensures that food transit is extremely effective and prevents numerous food waste on its own.

The web application has two major user interfaces, one for the beneficiary and the other for the patron. The typical information displayed at the beneficiary's end includes all the nearby food patrons. The "locality" typically has a radius of 15 to 20 kilometers. They have unrestricted access to all the available information about the consumables. The beneficiary's general information, mission, and vision are visible to the users on the patron's end. Users cannot select a specific beneficiary; they can only obtain information about where the food goes and how it benefitted. This helps ensure food security for all of our beneficiaries and enables us to avoid any prejudices. Each beneficiary's meal assignment is handled by the algorithm. By doing this, prejudices are further avoided, and food is served according to first come, first served. HTML, CSS, and ReactJS were used to construct the front end. Mongoddb is in charge of all backend operations. Expressjs is used to link the front end and back end.

CASE STUDY OF AN AUSTRALIAN GIRL IN FOOD REDISTRIBUTION

The following case study discusses how an countryside girl went on to become a CEO of food redistribution company [26]. Katy established a strong connection to the environment while growing up in the English countryside, surrounded by animals. While the environment has always been important to Katy, the issue of food waste first came to her attention when she operated an underground jazz bar in Melbourne. Katy saw there was a major problem and a tremendous chance to reform the system after witnessing the food waste caused by a single tiny bar. Because of her firsthand experience with food waste, she became the founding CEO of the food rescue group Second Bite, and the concept for Yume arose as a result of that experience. The two appear to be a natural match, so I left. But on my voyage there, I discovered that while many companies and farms cannot afford to give, there is more food than we could ever dream. As a result, a full community of solutions is required. Food rescue charities such as Second Bite, Oz Harvest, and Foodbank play an important role in preventing food waste and feeding people in need. However, some foods are not suitable for food rescue agencies, which is where Yume comes in. Second bite was doing good , But katy wanted to go and look at other food waste solutions since she knew Food Rescue couldn't do it all. There were too much And there is a lot of product that isn't always suitable for donation. There are other occasions when consumers require a return on their investment she encountered farmers who were abandoning their farms. because they were unable to make ends meet with their crops and standards. Some producers are unable to give excess food and want a return on that product while simultaneously decreasing food waste – Yume provides a new cash stream for struggling farms and producers. Furthermore, some food is not suitable for food rescue, such as pallets of ice cream taking up valuable and expensive fridge space that could otherwise be used for protein, which is essential for a healthy meal.

PROS

Provides food to those in need: We provide free or low-cost food to individuals and families who are struggling to afford groceries. This can help alleviate food insecurity and hunger, which can have negative impacts on physical and mental health. Reduces food waste, We often receive donations of surplus food from grocery stores, restaurants, and other sources. By distributing this food to people in need, food banks can help reduce food waste and its associated environmental impacts. Encourages community involvement, We often rely on volunteers to help sort and distribute food, which can provide an opportunity for people to get involved in their communities and help those in need. Provides emergency assistance, In addition to serving people who are experiencing chronic food insecurity, food banks can also provide emergency assistance to people who are facing unexpected financial challenges, such as a job loss or medical emergency.

CONS

May perpetuate underlying issues, provide short-term relief for hunger and food insecurity, they do not address the underlying issues that contribute to these problems, such as poverty and lack of access to affordable healthcare and education. In some cases, food banks may inadvertently perpetuate these issues by providing a temporary solution that does not address the root causes of poverty. Limited food options, we rely on donations from individuals and businesses, which can result in limited food options and nutritional variety. This can lead

to a dependence on processed and high-calorie foods, which can have negative health impacts.

Stigma and shame: Requiring individuals to rely on us or food banks can be stigmatizing and may cause feelings of shame or embarrassment. This can prevent people from seeking help and may contribute to a sense of isolation and marginalization. Can reinforce systemic issues, while food banks other organizations can provide immediate relief to people in need, they can also reinforce systemic issues by perpetuating the idea that charity and volunteerism are the primary solutions to poverty and food insecurity. This can distract from the need for systemic changes, such as raising the minimum wage and providing universal healthcare. Can lead to power imbalances: The reliance on donations from individuals and businesses can lead to power imbalances between the food bank and its donors. This can result in donations that are not always aligned with the needs of the people being served, or in food banks being beholden to the interests of their donors.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a successful solution to this problem may be an app that links hotels with people who are experiencing a food scarcity. Through a straightforward and user-friendly interface, the app enables hotels to give extra food to people in need, reducing food waste while also supplying vulnerable areas with vital nutrition. In addition to addressing the urgent needs of those who are food insecure, this strategy encourages businesses to be sustainable and socially responsible. As it enables real-time tracking and communication between hotels and food banks or other organizations that serve the poor, such an app can also help the distribution of food in a more organized and effective manner. In addition to lowering the likelihood of food waste and ensuring that more people have access to wholesome meals, this can assist guarantee that food is distributed fairly and equitably. Overall, a mobile app that links lodging facilities with those who are in need of food has the potential to have a big influence on the fight against hunger and food insecurity.

REFERENCES

1. Ishangulyyev, R., Kim, S. and Lee, S.H., 2019. Understanding food loss and waste—why are we losing and wasting food?. *Foods*, 8(8), p.297.
2. Herdt, R.W., 2004. Food shortages and international agricultural programs. *Critical reviews in plant sciences*, 23(6), pp.505-517.
3. Santeramo, F.G., 2021. Exploring the link among food loss, waste and food security: what the research should focus on?. *Agriculture & Food Security*, 10(1), p.26.
4. Salas-Bringas, C., Jeksrud, W.K. and Schüller, R.B., 2007. A new on-line process rheometer for highly viscous food and animal feed materials. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 79(2), pp.383-391.
5. Jyoti, D.F., Frongillo, E.A. and Jones, S.J., 2005. Food insecurity affects school children's academic performance, weight gain, and social skills. *The Journal of nutrition*, 135(12), pp.2831-2839.
6. Seligman, H.K., Laraia, B.A. and Kushel, M.B., 2010. Food insecurity is associated with chronic disease among low-income NHANES participants. *The Journal of nutrition*, 140(2), pp.304-310.
7. Kumar, S., Bansal, A., Shri, N., Nath, N.J. and Dosaya, D., 2021. Effect of food insecurity on the cognitive problems among elderly in India. *BMC geriatrics*, 21, pp.1-10.
8. Srivastava, S. and Muhammad, T., 2022. Rural-urban differences in food insecurity and associated cognitive impairment among older adults: findings from a nationally representative survey. *BMC geriatrics*, 22(1), p.287.

9. Fernandez, L., Das, M. and Angharia, J., 2020. Cascading Vulnerabilities: Food Insecurity Among Women in Disaster-Prone Areas in India. In *Disaster Studies: Exploring Intersectionalities in Disaster Discourse* (pp. 313-335). Singapore: Springer Singapore.
10. Tomiyama, J.M., Takagi, D. and Kantar, M.B., 2020. The effect of acute and chronic food shortage on human population equilibrium in a subsistence setting. *Agriculture & Food Security*, 9(1), pp.1-12.
11. Delgado, L., Schuster, M. and Torero, M., 2021. On the origins of food loss. *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 43(2), pp.750-780.
12. Agarwal, M., Agarwal, S., Ahmad, S., Singh, R. and Jayahari, K.M., 2021. Food loss and waste in india: the knowns and the unknowns. World Resources Institute India: Mumbai, India
13. Maxon, R.M., 2000. " Fantastic Prices" in the Midst of" An Acute Food Shortage:" Market, Environment, and the Colonial State in the 1943 Vihiga (Western Kenya) Famine. *African Economic History*, (28), pp.27-52.
14. Herdt, R.W., 2004. Food shortages and international agricultural programs. *Critical reviews in plant sciences*, 23(6), pp.505-517.
15. FAO. Food Wastage Footprint. Impacts on Natural Resource; Summary Report; Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations: Rome, Italy, 2013;
16. IRRI, Grain Storage: The IRRI Super Bag. Rice Science for a Better World. Rice Fact Sheets. 2005.
17. EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste. Recommendations for Action in Food Waste Prevention. Developed by the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste. 2019.
18. Rajeh, C., Saoud, I.P., Kharroubi, S., Naalbandian, S. and Abiad, M.G., 2021. Food loss and food waste recovery as animal feed: a systematic review. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 23, pp.1-17.
19. Georganas, A., Giamouri, E., Pappas, A.C., Papadomichelakis, G., Galliou, F., Manios, T., Tsiplakou, E., Fegeros, K. and Zervas, G., 2020. Bioactive compounds in food waste: A review on the transformation of food waste to animal feed. *Foods*, 9(3), p.291.
20. Truong, L., Morash, D., Liu, Y. and King, A., 2019. Food waste in animal feed with a focus on use for broilers. *International Journal of Recycling of Organic Waste in Agriculture*, 8, pp.417-429.
21. Nunuparov, M., Khotemlyansky, P., Popovich, A.E. and Panchishin, V., 2020, June. Wireless system of autonomous temperature and humidity sensors in potato storages. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1560, No. 1, p. 012051). IOP Publishing.
22. Truong, L., Morash, D., Liu, Y. and King, A., 2019. Food waste in animal feed with a focus on use for broilers. *International Journal of Recycling of Organic Waste in Agriculture*, 8, pp.417-429.
23. Yildiz, F., 2017. Initial preparation, handling, and distribution of minimally processed refrigerated fruits and vegetables. *Minimally processed refrigerated fruits and vegetables*, pp.53-92.
24. Negi, S. and Anand, N., 2015. Cold chain: a weak link in the fruits and vegetables supply chain in India. *IUP Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 12(1), p.48.
25. Australia, S.V., SecondBite case study: developing a future trust strategy for sustainability, viewed 29 June 2015.
26. Rajeh, C., Saoud, I.P., Kharroubi, S., Naalbandian, S. and Abiad, M.G., 2021. Food loss and food waste recovery as animal feed: a systematic review. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 23, pp.1-17.